

D7.3

Project

Website

BIOSCHAMP Project
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1.1.1.1 Disclaimer and acknowledgements

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101000651”

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Executive Summary

*This document is the “Project Website” presentation of the BIOSCHAMP Project, which is the **Deliverable 7.3 of the Work Package 7** (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation) of the Grant Agreement 101000651. This document presents the structure of the project website, which was initially in the “Preliminary plan for the dissemination of project results” included in the Grant Agreement (Part B, Section 2.2).*

The project website counts with 7 pages: home page, work plan, partners, results dissemination, media resources, news, and contact. The website has been designed respecting the project visual identity with a responsive and easy to navigate structure, making use of visual resources and a cohesive SEO strategy.

Finally, the website also complies with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 enforced on 25th of May 2018.

1 Introduction

This document describes the Website of the BIOSCHAMP project, the Deliverable 7.3 of the BIOSCHAMP Project (WP7). The document has been conceived and prepared by INNOVARUM (the commercial brand of EURIZON S.L., partner 7) and Work Package 7 leader (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation). INNOVARUM has developed the project webpage and will oversee the website maintenance, management, and necessary updates.

1.1 Scope of the document

This deliverable presents the project website structure, pages, sections, functionality, and SEO strategy. This document also includes comments on data protection, privacy concerns and the webpage cookie policy.

1.2 Objectives of the website

The main objectives of the website are:

- 1- Boost the Project digital presence across online platforms, supporting the project credibility.
- 2- Offer updated, dynamic, and visual content to all project audiences, mostly to the general public.
- 3- Maximise the general impact of the project and its results, building an easy-to access reference point for project partners as well as for external audiences (national, EU or international level) to get to know the project and its development.

2 General structure of the project website

The project website is located at <https://bioschamp.eu/>

The language of the webpage is English, and its basic structure includes the following pages:

- **Home Page.** It will include a summary of the BIOSCHAMP project and objectives.
- **Work Plan.** This page will show a description of the work packages (objectives, leading partner, and duration) together with a PERT diagram.
- **Partners.** This page will show a European map locating each partner, including each partner's brief description.
- **Results dissemination.** This page will contain BIOSCHAMP's practice abstracts and relevant publications.
- **Videos and media resources.** This page will host dissemination materials such: videos, flyers, and posters.
- **News.** News concerning the project's development will be published regularly in this section.
- **Contact.** This section will contain contact information and a form to subscribe to the project newsletter.

The website includes an **acknowledgement to the EU funding in all its pages in the footer section and a link the social media accounts in the static top main menu bar:**

Figure 1: acknowledgement to the EU funding, footer

Figure 2: link to social media channels in top main menu bar (Twitter and LinkedIn)

2.1 Website pages

This section includes captures and screenshots to visualise the current state of the project website (M6, March 2021). As it is possible to see, the webpage has made use of the visual identity of the project, creating a cohesive visual design.

2.1.1 Home

The home page has integrated a project presentation, infographics, call to action buttons to the "Work Plan Page" and "Partners" and structured the content in a visual and engaging way.

in

[Home](#) [Work Plan](#) [Partners](#) [Results dissemination](#) [Media resources](#) [News](#) [Contact](#) [Q](#)

About BIOSCHAMP

The BIOSCHAMP project aims to develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges: an alternative and sustainable peat-free biostimulant casing for the mushroom industry, reducing the dependency on and need for pesticides and contributing to improve the productivity, the sustainability, and the profitability of the European mushroom sector.

The goal of the BIOSCHAMP project is to improve the mushroom sector industrial profitability while reducing the agronomical need for pesticides by 90 %. This will help mushroom growers meet consumer demands to find alternatives to fungicide dependence.

OUR WORKPLAN

WHO MAKES IT POSSIBLE

12

International project partners

6

Countries

3.5 years

of project development

The mushroom cultivation process

The mushroom cultivation process involves 3 main steps:

1. Preparation of compost (substrate)
2. Application of the casing soil
3. Harvest of mushrooms

BIOSCHAMP will take part in this process providing an alternative and sustainable peat-free biostimulant.

CHALLENGES BIOSCHAMP FACES

The EU needs to accelerate the transition towards a pesticide-free mushroom sector

Diseases in the mushroom sector

The mushroom sector is heavily affected by diseases: currently, mycoparasites are responsible for the largest crop losses in commercial mushroom production.

Chemical products dependency

The EU mushroom sector depends greatly on chemical products (pesticides) to tackle disease appearance, however, they are not always sustainable.

Few tools to fight the problem

There are no adequate means of controlling diseases, mushroom growers struggle to find solutions as the number of allowed chemical products (pesticides) decreases.

NEWS

Last news of the BIOSCHAMP project

BIOSCHAMP begins, alternative sustainable biostimulant for the European mushroom industry

marzo 23rd, 2021 | Project meetings

BIOSCHAMP, a project that supports a greener and more sustainable Europe

The mushroom sector actively fosters circular economy sustainable models: mushroom cultivation reuses residual resources, working in line with the Circular Economy principles.

BIOSCHAMP will further facilitate circularity and resource efficiency in the EU mushroom sector through the development of a peat-free casing soil that will act as crop biostimulants.

Recent tweets

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101000651.

Contact points

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Jaime Carrasco:
j.carrasco@ctich.com

2.1.2 Work Plan

The Work Plan page presents the project work packages through a PERT diagram and provides some detail about them and about the partner that is carrying them out through a toggle element (*Work Packages in detail*). This page is also connected to the “Partners” page through a call-to-action button located after the toggle with content about the deliverables.

in

Home [Work Plan](#) [Partners](#) [Results dissemination](#) [Media resources](#) [News](#) [Contact](#) [Q](#)

BIOSCHAMP Work Plan

The implementation of the BIOSCHAMP project will be based on a 42-month Work Plan involving technical and commercial activities, divided into 9 Work Packages (WPs):

- ✓ **WP1**- Developing alternatives to peat-based casing material.
- ✓ **WP2**- Advanced Microbiota Optimisation
- ✓ **WP3**- Design of a biostimulant casing
- ✓ **WP4** - Validation
- ✓ **WP5** - Steps for industrialisation
- ✓ **WP6** - Security and sustainability
- ✓ **WP7** - Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
- ✓ **WP8** - Project management
- ✓ **WP9** - Ethics requirements

Work Packages in detail

WP1

Coordinated by Stichting Wageningen Research.

Duration: M1 – M18

Focus: evaluation of alternative casing materials to peat-based casing, involving laboratory assays and small-scale trials.

+ WP2**+ WP3****+ WP4****+ WP5****+ WP6****+ WP7****+ WP8****+ WP9**

BIOSCHAMP, making it happen

An international and multi-actor team has come together to work towards setting the grounds for a pesticide-free mushroom sector, safer for the environment, for the operators and for consumers.

[READ ABOUT BIOSCHAMP PROJECT PARTNERS](#)

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2.1.3 Partners

The Project partners tab offers content and details about each of the project partners, including their location in a graphic EU map and links to their respective webpages. It is possible to delve more into a partner organisation activity using the “flip boxes” element located below the partner’s map.

in

Home Work Plan **Partners** Results dissemination Media resources News Contact Q

BIOSCHAMP project partners

BIOSCHAMP is coordinated by one of the **Spanish Association of Mushroom Growers (ASOCHAMP)** which hosts the **Research Center of Mushroom (CTICH)**.

CTICH will work for 3.5 years together with research institutions – Inagro vzw (BE), Wageningen Research (NL), CSIC, University of Oxford (UK) -, key suppliers of the mushroom industry- KBVB (NL), world leader in providing substrate to mushroom growers and FERTINAGRO, large company specialised in fertilisers & plant protection products-, 1 large mushroom producer –EUROCHAMP (ES), –small mushroom producers – conventional UCLK (PL), organic EKOFUNGI (RS) and NF Fibre B.V. (NL) – and the innovation organisation active in the bioeconomy – Innovarum (ES).

<p>CTICH-PROJECT COORDINATOR</p> <p>CTICH is the Mushroom Technological Research Center of La Rioja, which is hosted by the Spanish Association of Mushroom Growers (ASOCHAMP). CTICH is also the current leader of the technical committee of the GEPC.</p> <p>KNOW MORE</p>	<p>Stichting Wageningen Research</p> <p>Partner 3</p>	
<p>EKOFUNGI</p> <p>Partner 6</p>		
<p>INNOVARUM-PARTNER 7</p> <p>INNOVARUM is a Spanish company created in 2013 with the overall aim of fostering innovation and knowledge exchange in the agri-food sector. Currently, it works as an innovation agent in the bioeconomy.</p> <p>KNOW MORE</p>	<p>KBVB</p> <p>Partner 9</p>	
<p>UOXF</p> <p>Partner 12</p>		

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2.1.4 Results dissemination

The dissemination page will be dedicated to public deliverables and publications on project results (including practice abstracts). For now, the page includes a “Coming soon” note until the content is ready.

[Home](#) [Work Plan](#) [Partners](#) [Results dissemination](#) [Media resources](#) [News](#) [Contact](#) [Q](#)

Coming soon!

As the project develops, this section will be updated to cover any relevant scientific publication or result.

This section will also include all public deliverables of the project.

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BIOSCHAMP Press Releases

BIOSCHAMP KOM 2021 PRESS RELEASE

Press Release, Madrid, 01/10/2020
BIOSCHAMP begins, alternative sustainable biostimulant for the European mushroom industry

The mushroom industry plays a key role in the EU's agri-food sector. Nationally, it provides a greenhouse alternative to animal products and it is a key source of vitamins D and selenium. (currently, it was valued at €13.7 billion in 2017 and projected to reach €66.8 billion in 2026 (CAER 18-17%).

Mushroom cultivation is a highly particular agricultural activity with a unique set of agronomical features and a high sensitivity to severe pathogens, which are responsible for major crop losses. Although chemical fungicides (pesticides) have been historically employed, regulatory limitations for mushroom growers and an increasing consumer awareness are urgently requesting solutions to overcome fungicide-dependence.

In this context, today a new European project has been launched. The BIOSCHAMP project aims to develop an integrated approach to tackle the mushroom cultivation challenges: an alternative and sustainable pest-free biostimulant using for the mushroom industry, reducing the dependence on and need for pesticides and contributing to improve the productivity, the sustainability, and the profitability of the European mushroom sector. The project will carry out validation at 4 different commercial mushroom farms to ensure the adaptability of the solution in real conditions.

BIOSCHAMP is a 3.5-year international initiative that is starting on 1st of October 2020 and will run until April 2024. The Mushroom Technological Research Center of La Alfranca (Instituto Madrileño de Producción de Setas y Hongos de La Alfranca, Research y Aragón (Spain) www.ictich.com) will coordinate the implementation of the project. The project counts with the participation of 12 partners from 6 different countries: CTIC (project coordinator, ES), Inagro vzw (BE), Sechring Biotechniques Research (NL), CMC (ES), Fertimagic Research (ES), Pathagel (ES), Innovatum (ES), EUROCHAMP (ES), Biotelia BVE (NL), NP Flare B.V. (NL), Lervara Gryplove Lulava Kvaute (PL) and University of Oxford (UK). In total, the project partners 3 Research Technological Centres, 3 large companies and 6 SMEs.

BIOSCHAMP is funded by the EU Commission Horizon 2020 Programme under the topic SP4-04-2019-2020 - Integrated health approaches and alternatives to pesticides use (Grant Agreement No.: 101000651) and counts with an overall budget of 4.2 million euros.

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2.1.6 News

The news page will be dedicated to project updates. At this point, the webpage contains a new about the project Kick Off Meeting.

Home Work Plan Partners Results dissemination Media resources **News** Contact Q

This section will include updates on the project development as well as relevant events. Stay tuned!

BIOSCHAMP begins, alternative sustainable biostimulant for the European mushroom industry

marzo 23rd, 2021

Recent Tweets

Tweets por @BIOSCHAMP

BIOSCHAMP H2020 project
@BIOSCHAMP

** Take a look at what is going on inside the growth chamber running at @ASOCHAMPRIORJA:

In today's picture you can see white button #mushroom crop exposed to #biostimulation for the #BIOSCHAMP project.

ctich.com/bioschamp/#H2020 #Bioeconomy #CircularEconomy

6h

Insertar Ver en Twitter

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Contact points

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2.1.7 Contact

The contact page covers all relevant project contact points and includes as well contact form to subscribe to the BIOSCHAMP newsletter. The subscription button includes a link to the website privacy policy, which is available to all users of the website to understand how their data is handled.

Home Work Plan Partners Results dissemination Media resources News **Contact** Q

Subscribe to our newsletter!

Organisation

Interests ?

Privacy consent: ?

I want to sign up to the BIOSCHAMP newsletter and accept the Privacy Policy consent.

SUBMIT

12

International project partners

6

Countries

3.5years

of project development

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3 SEO strategy

3.1 Design

The structure of the website is optimised so that user Experience (UX) as well as the User Interface Design (UI) is both responsive, attractive, and easy to access for all targets groups: from those familiar with webpages and technologies to those who might find digital resources a bit more daunting (for example, individual mushroom producers).

The responsive design adapts well to mobile devices and medium size devices, making sure users that enter the website through those enjoy a good experience.

3.2 Keywords

Keywords that the webpage uses to define its SEO position in Google Search (google.com) include relevant words for the project and sector such as BIOSCHAMP, mushroom production, mushroom sector, mushroom industry, circular economy, H2020, bioeconomy or sustainability... etc.

3.3 Outbound links

To boost SEO performance, the BIOSCHAMP webpage will be connected to all project partners webpages through external links to their respective webpages (located in “Partners page”). Additionally, by M6 (March 2020) all project partners will have included a mention to the BIOSCHAMP project in their respective websites. The mention to the project will follow the template provided for all partners in the “Basic DC Guidelines” provided short after the KOM by Innovarum, which present the project and make acknowledgement of the EU funding.

3.4 Inbound links

The webpage also makes use of internal links between its own pages. For example, from the home page to “Work Plan” and to “Partners” to engage users with the web content and avoid a high exit rate.

3.5 SSL certificate

Google Search values positively webpages with an updated SSL certificate. BIOSCHAMP has installed a valid and active SSL security certificate, which assures users that the website they visiting is safe from virus and general malware.

Image 1: BIOSCHAMP SSL certificate (Spanish)

4 Privacy and cookie policy

In compliance with the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679 enforced on 25th of May 2018, the BIOSCHAMP webpage informs all its users about its Privacy Policy and about the way users' data is handled. The BIOSCHAMP webpage does not collect any personal information from its users apart from those who wish to subscribe to the project newsletter.

For this case, as well as for the general tracking analytics data that might be collected, the BIOSCHAMP webpage has created its Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy, which offer all necessary information (GDPR compliant) to the data subjects.

- Privacy Policy: <https://bioschamp.eu/privacy-policy>
- Cookie Policy: <https://bioschamp.eu/cookie-policy>

If necessary, more details in this regard will be covered in *D9.3 : H - Requirement No. 4 of the WP9 Ethics requirements*

Following the latest GDPR requirements, content from third parties, tracking cooking (analytics purposes) and in general, non-necessary cookies; will not be active until the user consents to this through the cookie bar.

Image 2: Privacy and cookie policy permission bar

In case the wish to open it, users have more information on the type of cookies and consent they can provide at the Privacy policy and Cookie Policy information bar.

Image 3: Privacy policy and Cookie Policy information bar, extended

If they wish so, they can access here the Cookie Policy page and Privacy Policy page. In the first one (also available at the bottom of the webpage), they can change their cookie preferences at any time and check the full cookie list used:

Image 4: Update cookie preferences section

Update your cookie preferences here

Check the boxes of the cookies you want to be active in this webpage:

YouTube Vimeo Twitter Google Maps Tracking Cookies

UPDATE